

INTERNAL COMMUNICATION OF THE ORGANIZATION IN THE EMPLOYEE MUTATION PROCESS OF THE DIRECTORATE GENERAL OF CUSTOMS AND EXCISE IN 2024

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Abstract

This study aims to examine internal organizational communication in the employee transfer process at the Directorate General of Customs and Excise in 2024. This topic is important because employee transfers are an integral part of organizational dynamics and human resource management strategies. However, in practice, the process still raises various communication issues, such as delays in information delivery, unclear transfer patterns, and the emergence of anxiety and speculation among employees. This study employed a qualitative approach with a descriptive case study method. Data were collected through in-depth interviews with four executive employees who experienced transfers in 2024 and one informant from the personnel administration section, supported by observation and document analysis. The findings show that internal communication in the transfer process at the Directorate General of Customs and Excise is dominated by formal downward communication through decrees, official memoranda, and announcements in internal organizational media. However, this communication pattern tends to be one-way and does not adequately accommodate upward communication, resulting in limited opportunities for employees to express their aspirations, perceptions, and needs. In contrast, horizontal communication among colleagues functions relatively well and supports the adaptation process of transferred employees, particularly through the sharing of work experience, technical knowledge, and social support in the new work environment. From the perspective of the organizational socialization model, the transfer process has not been fully supported by open, participatory, and well-planned communication across the stages of anticipation, encounter, and metamorphosis. Transferred employees tend to seek information through direct questioning, disguised conversations, and observation of their new work environment. These findings confirm that the effectiveness of employee transfers is strongly influenced by the quality of internal organizational communication. Therefore, the Directorate General of Customs and Excise needs to develop a more transparent, two-way, fair, and well-structured communication pattern in the transfer process so that transfers are no longer perceived as a form of punishment, but rather as part of career development and organizational capacity building.

Keywords: *Internal Communication, Mutation Process, Depth Interview*

INTRODUCTION

This study aims to uncover internal organizational communication in the employee transfer process at the Directorate General of Customs and Excise in 2024. In the face of organizational dynamics and policy changes, employee transfers are a crucial aspect that every organization must manage well. Transfers within the Directorate General of Customs and Excise are commonplace (beacukai, 2024). Employee transfers involve the movement of employees from one work unit or location to another within the organization. Based on preliminary interviews, we uncovered communication issues in the employee transfer process at the Directorate General of Customs and Excise. The following is an excerpt from the initial interview conducted by the researcher:

"Honestly, I feel that information about transfers is often not communicated well to us. Several times I heard about transfers from other colleagues before hearing from our superiors. It feels unfair because receiving information about our future careers is our right as employees" (CL, pre-research, August 1, 2024)

Previously, transfers within the Directorate General of Customs and Excise were implemented as a form of disciplinary punishment for employees who committed integrity violations. However, there is currently no clarity regarding employee transfer patterns. As one of the researchers' initial interviewees stated:

“I would say there are some barriers to communication regarding transfers. There's a lack of clarity regarding transfer patterns. Some information is sometimes only circulated within certain circles, and this can cause concern and speculation among employees. All employees should have equal access to this information.” (MI, pre-research, August 1, 2024)

Furthermore, employee transfers are not just about the employee themselves. They also include their families, including their children who are already in school, and their spouses who are also pursuing careers.

“I think communication regarding transfers needs to be improved. Too often, we only learn about transfers close to the time of implementation. We should have had earlier notification, considering the impact on our personal and family lives.” (WCC, pre-research, August 1, 2024)

When individuals move from one job to another within an organization, they are typically not considered “new” employees and therefore are not provided with formal socialization experiences (Miller, 2015). However, these individuals still have to navigate new job requirements, new social relationships, and sometimes a new location (Miller, 2015). Research by Kramer (1993a) demonstrates the importance of communication during the job transfer process. Through communication, individuals who are transferring and their new coworkers exchange information to clarify their work and develop relationships. Communication from superiors during the transition phase and from colleagues throughout the process appears to contribute to the positive adjustment of individuals who are transferring. Because organizations will continue to move employees around in an effort to place the right people in the right positions, a greater awareness of how to facilitate the adaptation of individuals who are transferring through communication can help the organization and its members navigate the job transfer process.

According to Kotler (2000), communication involves several elements, including the sender (communicator), the message content, the communication channel (media), the recipient (receiver), the response, and feedback. A communicator must strive to ensure that their message is fully understood by the recipient. The process of sending messages among organizational members is called internal communication (Kambey, 2003). The members of the organization in question include subordinates and leaders, leaders and subordinates, and subordinates with subordinates, who interact with each other in organizational activities. Internal communication is the exchange of ideas between administrators and employees in a company or organization to realize company goals (Brennan, 1960), as well as to build and maintain relationships with internal publics designed by the company so that emotional closeness is created which is realized through commitment and involvement to achieve company goals (Woodruffe, 2006). The exchange of ideas takes place vertically and horizontally within the company so that the management process can be operationalized.

The Socialization Model in Organizational Communication outlined by Miller (2003) in his book illustrates that the assimilation process in organizations can be understood through several distinct stages. When an individual joins an organization, their adaptation does not occur instantly or immediately. Instead, adjustment to the organizational environment and culture typically takes time and progress. Researchers often group this process into three main stages: anticipation, socialization, encounter, and metamorphosis. Assimilation in organizational communication is achieved when individuals successfully integrate with the changes and systems in place within the organization. Therefore, one of the key factors influencing the success of the employee transfer process is effective internal communication. Internal communication is the exchange of information, views, and ideas between various members of the organization at all levels (Siregar et al., 2021). In the context of the employee transfer process, good internal communication can help create a clear understanding of the reasons, objectives, and mechanisms of the transfer, thereby reducing uncertainty and resistance among the employees involved (Siregar et al., 2021).

Transfers can be considered a form of change within an organization. Transfers refer to the movement or reassignment of employees from one position or department to another within the same organization. The purposes of transfers can vary, such as meeting organizational needs, developing employees, or filling vacant positions (Hasibuan, 2017). Transfers are part of the human resource management process and can help organizations optimize the use of employee skills and knowledge, reduce job burnout, and facilitate career development. Transfers can also help mitigate issues such as overstaffing in one department while understaffing in another (Hasibuan, 2017). Halim Nuswantoro, Head of the Personnel Subdivision (South Sulawesi Customs and Excise, 2024), explained that transfers are a strategy in human resource management (HR). Transfers are considered an intervention to improve employee capacity and performance by providing new exposure, experience, and assignments. Halim explained that the philosophy of transfers is to humanize employees and balance individual needs with organizational needs. Transfers can include competency development, recruitment, reward programs, disciplinary action, and Tour of Duty. The ideal duration of a transfer varies depending on the situation, but generally ranges from 2 to 5 years. Transfers are also expected to provide employees with new experiences, enabling them to develop technical skills, develop new

skills, and interact with different teams (South Sulawesi Customs and Excise, 2024). In the Decree of the Director General of Customs and Excise concerning Employee Transfers within the Directorate General of Customs and Excise in 2022, there were four employee transfers or reassignments at the Executive Level: 168 employees in April 2022, 851 employees in July 2022, 65 employees in October 2022, and 626 employees in December 2024. Meanwhile, in 2024, 343 executive employees were transferred in May 2024. In the context of the stigma surrounding transfers, the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DJBC) is making efforts to create a fair and planned internal transfer pattern. Employee perceptions are directed towards viewing transfers as development opportunities, not punishment. Good communication and competency mapping are key to eliminating the stigma of transfers (South Sulawesi Customs and Excise, 2024). Therefore, it is important to understand the internal communication landscape of employee transfer processes at the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DGCE) in 2024. Based on this background, we can understand the communication issues surrounding the transfer process from the perspective of DJBC employees. Previously, transfers within the DGCE were implemented as a form of disciplinary action for employees who committed integrity violations. However, there is currently no clarity regarding the employee transfer pattern. Furthermore, employee transfers are not solely about the employee themselves. They also require attention from their families, including school-aged children and spouses pursuing careers. An effective transfer process can impact overall organizational performance, as well as employee well-being and motivation.

This research focuses on the year 2024 for several important reasons. First, 2024 is the most recent period that provides relevant and up-to-date data on the employee transfer process at the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DJBC). This allows the research to capture the latest dynamics and policy changes that may have been implemented during that time. Second, based on initial interviews, it was discovered that there were significant communication issues in the employee transfer process in 2024. For example, several employees stated that information about transfers was often poorly communicated and that the transfer pattern was unclear. Third, the research focusing on a specific year allows for a more in-depth and focused analysis, resulting in more specific and useful findings for DJBC in improving its internal communication. Finally, by selecting 2024 as the time limit, this research can provide an overview of the organization's internal communication in the employee transfer process during that period. Furthermore, this research will also examine the socialization aspect of the transfer process. According to Kramer (1993a), communication is crucial during the transfer process. Communication from superiors during the transition phase and from coworkers throughout the process can contribute to the positive adjustment of transferred employees. As organizations continue to shift individuals in their efforts to place the right people in the right positions, raising awareness about how to facilitate the adaptation of transferred employees through communication can help organizations and their employees navigate the job transition process.

METHOD

This study on Internal Organizational Communication in the 2024 Directorate General of Customs and Excise Employee Transfer Process uses a qualitative approach. The researcher used a case study method. The type of research used is descriptive. The researcher used interviews as the main data collection technique in this study. Interviews were conducted with four informants from DJBC employees who had received a DJBC Decree regarding employee transfers within the DJBC environment who held executive positions, with a service period of more than two years, and had not experienced integrity issues during their work. These informants were selected because they met the criteria for informants from the perspective of employees affected by the 2024 Directorate General of Customs and Excise employee transfer process. The researcher also conducted an interview with one informant from the Personnel Administration Section. In this case, the identity of the research informants will be kept confidential by the researcher. The researcher also used observation as a data collection technique, as well as documents in the form of laws and regulations, DJBC communication product archives and other relevant documents as supporting data sources. The data assessment method used in this study is qualitative data analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Internal Communication of the Directorate General of Customs and Excise Organization in 2024

The role of communication in supporting organizational growth is crucial. Organizational communication is divided into two categories: internal and external. Internal communication is further subdivided into formal and informal. In this section, researchers will discuss internal communication, specifically the Internal Communication of the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DJBC) in 2024, both formal and informal, consisting of vertical and horizontal communication. Vertical communication encompasses communication from superiors to subordinates

and vice versa. Informants believe that downward communication is implemented formally, as evidenced by their statements that messages or information are delivered to subordinates through formal communication. At the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DJBC), this is implemented through decrees: "Every transfer is communicated through a decree signed by the Secretary General" (Interview with HS, Executive, January 10, 2024), service notes: "Only through service notes" (Interview with HT, Executive, January 11, 2024), and online announcements in DJBC's internal media. "Regarding DJBC transfers, information is conveyed through online announcements in DJBC's internal media" (Interview with K, Executive, January 12, 2024). Although some informants believed that top-down vertical communication had been implemented thoroughly, this was demonstrated by one informant's statement:

"It was communicated online and comprehensively, and an overview of the placement zones was provided" (Interview with HS, Executive, January 10, 2024).

"It was firmly stipulated in a decree regarding transfer regulations, which will be disseminated to all employees." (Interview with K, Executive, January 12, 2024)

However, other informants expressed differing views, stating that the messages conveyed were *"not comprehensive enough, with fragmented information"* (Interview with ES, Executive, January 9, 2024) and *"There was no good communication"* (Interview with HT, Executive, January 11, 2024). Referring to these informants' explanations, the researcher observed that the information conveyed by the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DJBC) was delivered through Decrees, Official Memors, and Announcements via DJBC's internal online media. These messages were communicated through one-way channels.

Therefore, it is understandable that downward communication is viewed favorably by some informants, but not favorably by others. This difference in opinion is likely due to the lack of accommodation for upward communication. Upward communication, however, plays a crucial role in conveying information from the bottom to the top, obtaining explanations, and further building strong employee understanding and loyalty to the organization. Informants believe that the implementation of upward communication has not been running well, as expressed by the following informants:

"I don't think the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DJBC) cares about employee perceptions. What's important is that employees implement what has been decided by the leadership." (Interview with HT, Executive, January 11, 2024)

"Every decision must be accepted; decisions must be implemented." (Interview with K, Executive, January 12, 2024)

"It would be very helpful if there was communication, but I haven't had that kind of communication." (Interview with ES, Executive, January 9, 2024)

Researchers believe that the opportunity for DJBC employees to convey messages upward has not been optimally accommodated. This means that employees' expectations for access to communication, including accurate, complete explanations delivered in a timely manner, are inadequate. Communication at DJBC includes not only communication between superiors and subordinates or subordinates and superiors, but also communication with colleagues and with other employees in different fields, which is carried out effectively. This was conveyed by several informants as follows:

"I teach the things I've done to my colleagues who weren't transferred and to my juniors before I was transferred." (Interview with HS, Executive, January 10, 2024)

"I teach my successors about their experiences and daily work. So that after I leave, their performance doesn't decline." (Interview with HT, Executive, January 11, 2024)

In contrast to vertical communication, which tends to be formal, the interviews revealed a more informal horizontal communication within the Directorate General of Customs and Excise. Informants also stated that horizontal communication between departments is well-conducted: *"Communication is carried out well, and assignments are immediately assigned to each section without discrimination."* (Interview with HS, Executive, January 10, 2024)

This indicates that the implementation of internal organizational communication at the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DGCE) is good, both for downward and lateral communication. Meanwhile, informants stated that the condition of internal communication at the Directorate General of Customs and Excise is not good. Interviews with several DGCE employees revealed that upward communication at the Directorate General of Customs and Excise tends to focus on conveying decisions and instructions from the leadership level. Employees feel that their perceptions are not taken seriously, with the priority being the implementation of decisions already taken. While there is recognition that better communication would be helpful, in practice, such communication is

still perceived as lacking. This suggests potential for improving upward communication at the Directorate General of Customs and Excise to be more inclusive and to pay greater attention to employee perceptions and needs.

3.2 Internal Organizational Communication Regarding the 2024 Directorate General of Customs and Excise Mutation Process

Furthermore, Miller's (2003) Socialization in Organizational Communication model explains communication as a means of change. For example, in the anticipation stage of socialization, organizational communication plays a crucial role in providing initial information about upcoming changes or transfers. This information helps employees understand the reasons behind the transfer and prepare themselves mentally and emotionally. In this section, the researcher will describe how the socialization process at the Directorate General of Customs and Excise in 2024 relates to the transfer process that has been implemented. When an employee joins an organization, adaptation does not occur automatically and immediately. Rather, adjustment to organizational life takes time and gradually, which in the context of this research concerns employee transfers. This can be explained through the stages of the Socialization Process in Organizations, specifically Miller's (2015) Socialization in Organizational Communication Model.

As Hasibuan (2017) stated, the principle of transfer emphasizes moving employees to appropriate positions and jobs with the aim of increasing work enthusiasm and productivity. In this context, interview results regarding openness and transparency in the transfer process and experiences related to transfer policies can be linked to the principles of transfer outlined by Hasibuan. Interview results indicate that openness and transparency in the transfer process are inadequate. According to Hasibuan, the principle of transfer emphasizes appropriate transfers to improve morale and productivity. A lack of transparency can hinder the achievement of these goals, as employees lack a sufficient understanding of transfer decisions. Hasibuan (2017) lists three basic systems for implementing transfers: the seniority system, the spoil system, and the merit system. Criticism of transfer policies, which may not always be objective or fair, as expressed in the interviews, can be attributed to the weaknesses of the seniority and spoil systems. The merit system is described as a sound basis for implementing employee transfers. Interview results indicated that employees were dissatisfied with transfers that did not meet their expectations, and a merit system can help assess transfers based on work performance, objectivity, and scientific basis. The merit system criteria, which include increased work motivation, reduced errors, better attendance, maintained discipline, and reduced accidents, align with Hasibuan's expectations regarding the purpose of transfers. Interview statements highlight the importance of a fair and neutral transfer policy. This aligns with Hasibuan's understanding that implementing a transfer system effectively requires a fair and neutral policy and a clear understanding by each employee.

Summarizing these aspects, it can be concluded that to achieve the desired goal of transfers, organizations need to increase transparency, avoid non-objective transfer policies (such as the spoil system), and support the implementation of a merit system with a fair and neutral transfer policy. Therefore, considering the socialization conducted by the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DJBC) for employees, when linked to the socialization process according to Miller (2012), the following can be identified: First, Anticipatory Socialization. In the anticipatory socialization process, the organization's internal communication focuses on new employees before they join the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DJBC). New employees receive detailed socialization regarding the duties and organizational structure of the DJBC during orientation. This process includes information on relevant regulations and responsibilities, which helps them prepare before officially joining. Existing employees do not receive similar socialization during transfers, as they are expected to already understand their core duties based on existing regulations and the new Organizational Governance Structure (SOTK). Therefore, new employees are usually better prepared for change than existing employees, who may have difficulty adjusting to new tasks..

Second, meetings. The socialization process at the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DGCE) occurs when both existing and newly transferred employees begin to adapt to their new positions or divisions. Newly transferred employees must abandon their old habits and adopt new ones suited to their new work environment. New employees tend to adapt more quickly because they have fewer old habits to unlearn. Conversely, newly transferred employees may face obstacles in abandoning old habits, which can trigger negative reactions to their performance, such as demotivation. This process requires strong internal communication support to help newly transferred employees overcome resistance to change. Third, metamorphosis. The metamorphosis stage describes the situation in which employees, both existing and newly transferred, are finally able to accept and adapt to the changes. At this stage, DJBC employees begin to feel comfortable with their new tasks and positions and operate in accordance with organizational expectations. Internal communication plays a crucial role in ensuring that all employees understand the changes and can work effectively in the new work environment. This process involves two-way communication

between management and employees, where the company must be responsive to employee feedback and reactions to create alignment. In communicating important organizational information, particularly regarding employee transfers, there must be a reciprocal process that is accepted by both parties, both the communicator and the recipient. As defined in the communication process, reciprocity in communication between the organization and employees is also essential. Effective communication between the organization and employees must be reciprocal. As outlined in the research findings and previous discussions, from the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DJBC) perspective, the detailed communication process and resulting reciprocal process in socializing information to all DJBC employees, both transferred and new employees, are slightly different. At DJBC, socializing changes in status and new duties to newly transferred employees requires a more personalized approach to address reactions and resistance to changes in their duties and work locations. Active and interactive communication between management and newly transferred employees helps align perceptions and organizational goals. Providing clear and detailed information and handling complaints or revolts from newly transferred employees are part of a reciprocal communication process.

Miller, V. D. & Jablin, F. M. (1991) classified seven tactics that organizational members may use when trying to gather or search for information about the organization (Miller, 2012), namely: (1) Overt questions: New members or employees seek information by asking direct questions, (2) Indirect questions: New members or employees seek information by asking hint questions, (3) Third parties: New members or employees seek information by asking a second source, (4) Testing limits: New members or employees seek information by violating organizational rules and observing reactions, (5) Disguising conversations: New members or employees gather information by disguising their search for information and attempting to make it a natural part of the conversation, (6) Observing: New members or employees gather information by observing behavior in prominent situations, (7) Surveillance: New members or employees gather information by understanding behavior observed in the past.

Based on the results of research on internal organizational communication in the 2024 DJBC employee transfer process, which was carried out by transferred employees, it shows that the transferred employees only used a few tactics in seeking information. For transferred employees, the tactics used to gather useful information about their new tasks and workplace are: first, overt questions, which involves seeking information by asking questions directly within the organization. In this case, this can be done with the direct management team or coworkers. Second, disguised conversations, where employees gather various information about their new tasks and workplace by disguising the information-seeking process as natural conversations. And third, observing, where employees observe the behavior of their coworkers in the new workplace. The goal of these tactics is to gain a better understanding of the organization's culture and new work environment, allowing them to adapt more quickly.

Employee transfers at the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DJBC) are unavoidable as they are stipulated in applicable regulations. This policy primarily impacts employees who undergo transfers. Transfers are a process that ensures employee movement within the organization aligns with operational needs and management strategy. Within this process, socializing transfers to affected employees is a primary focus of internal organizational communication. The information provided typically includes a list of employees to be transferred and their new positions. However, when it comes to employee readiness for transfers, various reactions must be managed. Transferred employees often undergo a lengthy and complex negotiation process, given that transfer decisions can elicit a variety of emotional and practical reactions. These reactions can include worry, uncertainty, or even resistance to the change. Therefore, achieving acceptance of transfer decisions often requires considerable time and intensive support from management. It is clear that perceived organizational support is a desired and beneficial outcome for the organization. Meanwhile, from an employee perspective, they are attracted to organizations that meet or exceed their career expectations and personal goals (Arasanmi & Krishna, 2019).

The internal communication conducted by the Directorate General of Customs and Excise during the transfer process was quite effective in managing interactions with employees. DJBC management strived to provide clear and timely information to transferred employees and responded to their questions and concerns. However, there are aspects that still need improvement, namely in terms of socialization and adaptation to the new status of transferred employees. Through internal communication, organizations can create and maintain a communication system between the organization and employees (Tkalac Verčič, 2021) and represent the transfer of ideas, information, attitudes, and emotions among employees (Bahtijarević-Siber & Sikavica, 2001). Effective internal communication is crucial to organizational success (Ruck & Welch, 2012). It can improve internal relationships and communication between employees and managers (Welch, 2012). If managed carefully, internal communication can increase awareness of threats and opportunities. On the other hand, this can pose risks if communication is poor (Tkalac Verčič, 2021). The importance of this communication was also conveyed by informant X from the Personnel

Administration Section of the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DJBC):

"That's why communication is necessary. This transfer is part of broadening the horizons and exposure of each employee to broaden their understanding. The job spectrum varies widely, from highly technical ones that engage with others and external stakeholders to highly administrative ones. Everyone has different talents. With proper mapping, this should be captured so that we can at least determine their strengths, whether we want them to be specialists or generalists." (Interview with X, Personnel Administration Section, July 6, 2024)

However, based on the interview results, it was revealed that the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DJBC) has not yet made any efforts to manage internal communication regarding employee transfer processes within the DJBC. This is implied in the following excerpt from an interview with informant X from the Personnel Administration Section:

"Yes, sometimes when someone is transferred to a remote location, it feels like they are being punished. For example, if Mr. Irsan is transferred to Surabaya, do you feel punished? Therefore, in the Personnel Administration Sub-Section, we are in the process of creating an internal transfer pattern. The hope is that with this internal transfer pattern, the criteria and deadlines are clear, so everyone can predict when to prepare for a transfer. So, transfers are inevitable, and everyone will get their turn to receive new exposure fairly. Therefore, the perception should not feel like a punishment. With good mapping, we ensure that each work unit has a balanced proportion of troublemakers, ideal employees, and exceptional employees. This way, each work unit also has equal responsibilities. So, there is no such thing as a transfer as punishment. This concerns "Employee aspirations too. It could be because their home base is here, and if they're far away, they feel punished. Yet, we've committed from the start to being able to be placed anywhere as part of our contract with the country. Ideally, we try to implement a transfer pattern that prioritizes employee aspirations, taking into account the interests of the organization and trying to balance the needs of both parties. That's what Mr. Irsan said." (Interview with X, Personnel Administration, July 6, 2024)

In conveying important information about the organization, there must be a reciprocal process that is accepted by both parties, both the communicator and the recipient, as defined by the communication process. This reciprocal process in communication between the organization and employees is also crucial. As explained in previous research and discussions, from the perspective of the organization, the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DJBC), a detailed communication process that generates reciprocity in the socialization of transfers to all employees still lacks a clear pattern. In terms of socialization of employee transfers, communication with employees emphasizes one-way communication, as an order, as part of the "employment contract with the state."

"This also concerns employee aspirations. Perhaps because their home base is here, being far away feels like a punishment. Yet, we have committed from the start to be able to be placed anywhere as part of our contract with the state." (Interview with X, Personnel Administration Division, July 6, 2024)

Based on the discussion above, internal communication at the DJBC during the 2024 transfer process played a crucial role in helping newly transferred employees adapt to the changes they faced. The socialization process of anticipation, encounter, and metamorphosis requires different communication approaches, depending on the needs and challenges faced by employees. The reciprocal process of communication between the organization and employees, as well as the use of various information-gathering tactics, helps create an adaptive and harmonious work environment. This process is known as assimilation. According to Jablin and Putnam (2001), organizations attempt to influence their members by providing a wealth of information about the organization to align goals within the organization (Miller, 2012). However, on the other hand, organizational members also undergo their individualization process to adapt to the organizational environment, such as adjusting to the work system and rules within the organization. Employees are provided with explanations and socialization so they can accept the mutations that occur.

CONCLUSION

Internal communication at the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DJBC) in 2024 had two dimensions: vertical and horizontal communication. Vertical communication from superiors to subordinates at DJBC tended to be formal, delivered through decrees, official memos, and online announcements. There was an unmet need for bottom-up vertical communication, where employees felt their perceptions were ignored and communication from above was more instructive than inclusive. On the other hand, horizontal communication between departments at DJBC was assessed as good and inclusive, indicating potential for improving upward communication to better address employee perceptions and needs. The transfer process is part of the organizational routine, but for employees, it represents a crucial adaptation period. Formal communications, such as decrees and

official memos, were delivered through NADINE and WhatsApp groups. However, communication gaps related to transfer procedures were noted, with some employees expressing a lack of clarity and necessary communication during the socialization phases. First, the anticipatory socialization phase, focused on the initial socialization before the transfer, where employees expected information and preparation regarding the upcoming changes. Second, encounter. Communication at this stage includes self-introduction, creating a performance contract, and providing guidance regarding new tasks and the work environment. Third, metamorphosis. Communication at this stage supports the transition from "outsider" to "insider" status by facilitating a deeper understanding of the tasks, organizational culture, and interpersonal relationships in the new workplace.

Stages of the organizational socialization process, such as anticipatory socialization and encounter, are crucial to helping transferred employees adapt. Furthermore, communication during the transfer process also influences employees' emotional responses to change, which can vary depending on factors such as the transfer location and support from superiors and coworkers. The importance of effective communication during the transfer process is also emphasized, including providing transferred employees with the necessary tools to prepare them for adaptation to the new environment. Overall, the internal communication process during employee transfers requires careful attention to facilitate smooth adaptation and minimize negative impacts on employee performance and motivation. In managing transfers, it is important to strike a balance between the needs of the organization and individual employees, and to foster awareness of individual needs and expectations, which can be achieved through internal organizational communication.

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